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Department [Project Management](#)

NAUTILOS Final Quality Plan

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DEC	Websites, patents, filing, etc.	
DEM	Demonstrator	
O	Other	

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CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
GA	Grant Agreement
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
CP	Consortium Partners
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
TL	Task Leader
TcL	Task Co-Leader
TIB	Technical and Innovation Board
TIM	Technical and Innovation Manager
OCM	Outreach, Communication & Dissemination
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
RAM	Responsibility Assignment Matrix
RASCI	Variant of the RAM (responsible, accountable, supporting, consulted, informed)
RWPL	Reviewing Work Package Leader
TL	Task Leader
WPL	Work Package Leader
WPcL	Work Package Co-Leader

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NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: <http://www.nautilus-h2020.eu/>.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The following document comprises the quality management and control procedures which have been proven to work within the first 24 months of the project lifetime and are to be followed in the execution of the NAUTILOS project.

In particular, the aim of this deliverable is to update the mechanisms that will be applied throughout the project in order to ensure the quality level of project deliverables and results. Very few updates were made in the first version of the Quality Plan because the drafted Quality Plan (D1.4) has proven to be monitoring and controlling the project progress successfully so far, thus the present version of the Quality Plan is non-separable from the initial D1.4, making the needed references to the respective sections and descriptions in D1.4.

The initial version of the Quality Plan was followed strictly and used as a tool to monitor and assess the project's status, risks, and quality progress, therefore the PM team considered no major updates were needed as a whole based on the first 2 years of the project, except for some minor changes being the following mentioned below:

- Chapter III: Quality Management – change in the TIB Manager
- Chapter IV: Project Budget – Lump Sum - NAUTILOS is a H2020 lump sum pilot project. A table with the budget has been added to the present version of the Quality Plan.
- Chapter VI: Project Progress Measurement – WP status reports are gathered every 2 months (instead of 1 as it was planned in the first version of the WP) by the WPLs containing information about progress, risks, issues, deviations from the plans, mitigation measure. Also new Meetings were introduced – WPL meeting between the WPLs – once every 3 months (every second one is during the CM).

I. INTRODUCTION

The NAUTILOS Project Final Quality Plan is an update of a key deliverable for WP1 which is aiming to provide a single point of reference on the quality assurance tools and procedures that will be applied along the NAUTILOS project. The original deliverable D1.4 together with its update – the present document, is intended to serve as a guide for all Consortium members when a specific question needs to be answered for many day-to-day activities. As its guiding purposes, this deliverable provides a harmonized set of indication, procedures, and support documents to be used by all partners for an effective quality implementation of the project.

The present form represents the official document submitted to the European Commission in compliance with Grant Agreement commitments.

Being an integral part of management planning, providing a common standard to be applied throughout the entire project life, the Quality Plan defines a set of procedures to be followed to secure that:

- the Grant Agreement requirements and conditions have been fully applied and followed by all partners,
- EU/national regulations are considered in operational, administrative, and financial management,
- all rights and obligations defined in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement are fulfilled,
- all project activities are implemented in accordance with the Work Plan (as described in the Grant Agreement).

II. QUALITY OBJECTIVES

The Final Quality Plan is intended to provide updated guidance for ensuring the achievement of high-quality project results and smooth project implementation regarding completion of the project's tasks on time, on budget, in scope and in line with the contractual obligations with EC, as well as with all relevant rules and provisions.

The main objectives of this document are:

- The project's quality characteristics are defined, agreed, and achieved throughout the project,
- Quality assurance tools and procedures are performed as planned, including assuring compliance with EU's rules and regulations,
- Quality control activities are performed as planned,
- Any non-conformity (or opportunity for quality improvements) is identified and corrected (or implemented),
- Deliverables are accepted by the respective project partners based on the defined quality/acceptance criteria,
- Project documents (project final and interim reports) are accepted by the respective project partners based on the defined quality/acceptance criteria.

III. QUALITY MANAGEMENT

Project quality management aims to ensure that the current project will meet the expected results in the most efficient way and that deliverables will be accepted by the relevant stakeholders. It involves overseeing all activities needed to maintain a desired level of excellence. This includes creating and implementing quality planning and assurance, as well as quality control and quality improvement.

1. QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROCESS AND TOOLS

The NAUTILOS project defines a set of procedures to be performed and followed throughout the project to facilitate the quality management process.
There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p. 10).

2. PROJECT MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE

NAUTILOS has 21 partners from 11 European countries and is coordinated by CNR.

The project management structure of NAUTILOS is outlined in Figure 1 below as there has been no change since D1.4 was submitted - for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p. 12).

The management structure and applied procedures are established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) and are described in detail in D1.1 Report on Management Procedures.

Figure 1. NAUTILOS Project Management Structure

3. PROJECT GOVERNING BODIES

There has been no change in the Project Governance: GA, TIB, EAB.

a. General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA) is the ultimate decision-making body of the Consortium, which consist of one representative per partner and is chaired by the PC.

The role, responsibilities, process and schedule of the GA have been detailed in D1.1 Report on Management Procedures (M3) and D1.4 Quality Plan (M3).

b. Technical and Innovation Board

Technical and Innovation Board (TIB) is the supervisory Consortium Body for the technical implementation of NAUTILOS which reports to and is accountable to the General Assembly.

The role, responsibilities, process and members of the TIB has been detailed in D1.1 Report on Management Procedures (M3) and D1.4 Quality Plan (M6).

c. External Advisory Board

The External Advisory Board acts as an independent external body, chaired by the Coordinator and composed of external experts.

The role, responsibilities, process and members of the EAB has been detailed in D1.1 Report on Management Procedures (M3), D1.4 Quality Plan (M3) and D1.2 External Advisory Board Report 1 (M12).

4. PROJECT MANAGEMENT ROLES

An in-depth description of each of the project management roles established within NAUTILOS is to be found in D1.1 Report on Management Procedures (M3) and D1.4 Quality Plan (M3).

The only change in the management bodies is the shift concerning the person appointed as the Technical and Innovation Manager (described below).

The project organisational structure of NAUTILOS is outlined in Figure 2 as there has been a change in the Technical and Innovation Manager (TIM) – Catarina Lemos (CeiiA) replaced Armindo Torres (CeiiA).

Figure 2. NAUTILOS Organisational Structure

a. Project Coordinator

The Project Coordinator (PC), Gabriele Pieri from CNR, is responsible for the coordination and management of the overall project.

b. Data Controller

The Data Controller (DC), Antonio Novellino from ETT, is responsible for the data management and the data management plan within NAUTILOS.

c. Technical and Innovation Manager

The Technical and Innovation Manager (TIM), Catarina Lemos from CEiiA (a successor of the former TIM, Armindo Torres from CEiiA) supervises and directs the technical and innovation aspects of the project.

Catarina Lemos is a Project Manager at CEiiA, bringing experience from previous roles at UACOOPERA, Universidade de Aveiro, CESAM (University of Aveiro, Portugal) and Sines Tecnopolo. Catarina Rasquilha Lemos holds a 2019 - 2020 Marinheiro 2° Classe - Tráfego Local in Embarcações Tráfego Local @ For-Mar. With a robust skill set that includes Seismology, Environmental Engineering, GIS, Remote Sensing, Science and more, Catarina Lemos contributes valuable insights to the industry.

d. Project manager

The administrative and project manager, Victoria Geraskova from EP (acting as a substitute of Natali Dimitrova, the former project manager), is responsible for the administrative follow up of the project.

e. Work Package Leaders

At the operational level, the work of the project is divided into 13 work packages. Each Work Package will be led by a Work Package Leader (WPL), supported by WP co-leaders, task and sub-task leaders.

5. PARTNER CONTACT DETAILS

Contact details of the representatives of all partner organisation in NAUTILOS can be found under the project's ownCloud and Google Drive shared spaces. These are subject of periodic review and update (every 6 months). No change has been made in this respect.

6. PERT DIAGRAM: WORK BREAKDOWN STRUCTURE

No changes has been made in the project's composition in terms of structure and links between the WPs and tasks.

Figure 3. NAUTILOS PERT Diagram

7. GANTT CHART: PROJECT SCHEDULE

To manage the complexity of the NAUTILOS project, a detailed GANTT Chart (expanded from the initial basic GANTT chart version) providing a visual overview of the project schedule has been prepared and is available in OwnCloud shared space. To best fit the complex organisation of NAUTILOS activities, the GANTT has been constructed around a multi-level structure with specific timeframes per work package, per task and per sub-task. It also contains information about the involved partners in each task/WP, connected tasks/WPs, start and end date; percentage of progress of each task/WP, if there is a risk for its completion as planned and if the milestones have been achieved.

The GANTT chart is meant to serve as a management supporting tool, as well as a progress monitoring tool for following up the activities development at WP, task and sub-task level.

The GANTT chart is to be regularly (every 2 months) updated by the project partners.

An extract of NAUTILOS GANTT chart is provided below (fig.4).

Actions	Category	Assigned to	Participating partners	Progress	Initial Plan	Start	End date	Start NAU Month	End NAU Month	related task (WP2 table)
WP1. Project Management										
T1.1 Scientific and Technical Project Management	On Track	CNR	All	40%	40%	10/1/2020	10/1/2024	M1	M48	ALL WPs
T1.2 Communication and Administrative Project Management	On Track	EP	All	40%	40%	10/1/2020	10/1/2024	M1	M48	
ST1.2.1 'Internal Project Management Tools	On Track	EP	All	40%	40%	10/1/2020	10/1/2024	M1	M48	
ST1.2.2 'Creation of Project Management Tools	On Track	EP	All	40%	40%	10/1/2020	10/1/2024	M1	M48	
ST1.2.3 'Administrative Support to consortium members and Project Governing Bodies	On Track	EP	All	40%	40%	10/1/2020	10/1/2024	M1	M48	
T1.3 External Advisory Board	On Track	CNR	All	40%	40%	10/1/2020	10/1/2024	M1	M48	
T1.4 Data Management Plan	On Track	CNR	All	40%	40%	10/1/2020	10/1/2024	M1	M48	WP8
T1.5 Quality Assurance	On Track	EP	All	40%	40%	10/1/2020	10/1/2024	M1	M48	
T1.6 Ethics in the context of marine observation	On Track	CNR	All	40%	40%	10/1/2020	10/1/2024	M1	M48	WP13
WP2. Technical Requirements										
T2.1 Political and societal drivers and requirements	On Track	CNR	CNR, HCMR, NIVA, SYKE, IFREMER, ETT SPA, EDGELAB, NKE, AQIATEC, CEIHA, HES-SO.	100%	100%	10/1/2020	7/1/2021	M1	M9	WP3, 4, 5, 7
T2.2 Technical requirements, standard sensor system and architecture	On Track	NIVA	HCMR, NIVA, SYKE, IFREMER, ETT, IFREMER, Aquatec, NKE, HES-SO, IFFI, HES-SO, FRODO, FRODO, HES-SO	100%	100%	10/1/2020	7/1/2021	M1	M9	
T2.3 Requirements for integration of sensors into selected platforms, incl. communication interfaces	On Track	SCT	NIVA, CNR, SYKE, Aquatec, NKE, HES-SO	100%	100%	10/1/2020	7/1/2021	M1	M9	
Specifications completed	Milestone	SCT		100%	100%	7/1/2021				M9 WP3, WP4
WP3. Biogeochemical and Biological Instrument Development										
T3.1 Fluorometric Sensors	On Track	AQIATEC	MR, NIVA, SYKE, NKE, HES-SO, DI	100%	100%	10/1/2020	4/1/2022	M1	M18	
ST3.1.1 Fluorometric Sensor	On Track	HES-SO	NKE, SYKE	100%	100%	10/1/2020	4/1/2022	M1	M18	
ST3.1.2 Dissolved Oxygen and Fluorescence Sensors	On Track	NKE		100%	100%	10/1/2020	4/1/2022	M1	M18	
T3.2 Downward-looking sensors for ocean platforms and aerial drones	On Track	NIVA	HCMR, DFKI	100%	100%	10/1/2020	4/1/2022	M1	M18	T 6.2, T9.4, T5.2
T3.3 Passive Acoustic Sensors	On Track	AQIATEC	HES-SO	100%	100%	10/1/2020	4/1/2022	M1	M18	
ST3.3.1 Passive broadband acoustic recording sensor for noise monitoring	On Track	AQIATEC		100%	100%	10/1/2020	4/1/2022	M1	M18	T 5.4, T6.1.5, T7
ST3.3.2 Passive acoustic event recorder	On Track	AQIATEC		100%	100%	10/1/2020	4/1/2022	M1	M18	T 5.4, T6.1.5, T7
T3.4 Active Acoustic Profiling Sensor	On Track	AQIATEC		100%	100%	10/1/2020	4/1/2022	M1	M18	5.4, T6.1.6, T7.2
T3.5 Sampler for phytoplankton and other suspended matter	On Track	NIVA	HCMR, SYKE, DFKI	100%	100%	10/1/2020	4/1/2022	M1	M18	

Figure 4. NAUTILOS GANTT Chart (WP1 – WP3 partial overview)

8. OPENPM²: OPEN PROJECT MANAGEMENT METHODOLOGY

NAUTILOS has adopted and utilises the OpenPM², a project management methodology designed by the European Commission. All NAUTILOS templates have been designed to fully answer the methodology's requirements.

IV. PROJECT BUDGET – LUMP SUM

NAUTILOS is a H2020 lump sum pilot project.

The approved project's budget and the person-months summary table on a per task level are providing a clear overview of the effort different partners involved in a respective task and can be found in the project's OwnCloud shared space. The table for distribution of the staff effort of the beneficiaries is included below to clearly outline and be the final reference point for the distribution of the person months on task level

Table 1: Summary table with Person-Months:

	CNR	HCMR	NIVA	SYKE	IFREMER	CNRS	ETT	EL	UALG	NKE	Aquatec	SCT	CEIHA	TP	HESSO	CSEM	UL-FE	EurOcean	DFKI	DIATIC	IMAR	EP	TOTAL PM	
WP1	33.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.5	4.0	1.0	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	-	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	19.0	72.8	
T1.1	16.0	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	2.0	22.8
T1.2	2.0	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	1.3	-	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.2	-	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	10.0	17.5	
T1.3	5.0	-	0.2	0.3	0.1	-	-	-	0.1	-	0.3	0.3	0.2	-	0.2	-	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.8	8.1	
T1.4	7.0	-	0.1	-	0.1	-	2.5	-	0.2	-	-	-	0.1	-	0.1	-	0.1	0.2	0.2	-	0.2	0.3	11.0	
T1.5	1.0	-	0.1	-	0.1	-	-	0.8	0.2	-	-	-	0.2	-	0.1	-	0.1	0.2	0.2	-	0.2	5.0	8.2	
T1.6	2.0	-	0.1	0.3	0.1	-	-	-	0.2	-	0.3	0.3	0.1	-	0.2	-	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	1.0	5.2	
WP2	3.5	2.5	3.0	1.5	1.3	-	1.0	2.0	-	1.0	11.0	3.0	-	0.5	0.5	2.0	-	1.0	-	-	-	-	34.8	
T2.1	3.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.0	
T2.2	-	0.5	2.0	-	0.3	-	1.0	-	-	0.5	0.5	2.0	-	-	0.3	0.5	1.0	-	0.5	-	-	-	9.0	
T2.3	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	-	-	2.0	-	0.5	0.5	9.0	3.0	-	0.3	-	1.0	-	0.5	-	-	-	-	19.8	
WP3	-	1.0	7.0	4.0	-	-	-	-	-	27.0	28.5	-	-	-	8.0	-	-	-	3.0	-	-	-	78.5	
T3.1	-	-	-	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	27.0	-	-	-	-	5.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	33.5	
T3.2	-	0.5	3.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.0	-	-	-	6.3	
T3.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.0	-	-	-	2.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	14.5	
T3.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16.5	
T3.5	-	0.5	-	3.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.0	-	-	-	4.5	
T3.6	-	-	3.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.3	
WP4	1.0	25.5	9.0	-	-	21.0	6.0	-	-	14.0	-	31.5	-	-	20.0	16.0	-	2.0	-	-	-	-	146.0	
T4.1	-	-	3.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.3	
T4.2	-	-	-	-	-	21.0	-	-	-	12.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	33.0	
T4.3	0.5	-	3.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	22.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.0	-	-	-	27.8	
T4.4	0.5	-	2.5	-	-	-	6.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	29.0	
T4.5	-	3.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.0	-	7.5	-	-	-	-	16.0	-	-	-	-	-	28.5	
T4.6	-	22.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	22.5	
WP5	6.0	4.0	5.0	2.0	1.5	16.5	-	63.5	-	12.0	3.5	16.0	50.0	-	2.5	1.0	-	-	-	33.5	-	-	217.0	
T5.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	51.0	-	-	1.5	-	6.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	58.5	
T5.2	-	-	2.0	-	-	-	-	10.5	-	-	1.0	13.0	38.0	-	-	-	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	65.0	
T5.3	5.5	2.0	2.3	2.0	1.5	-	-	-	-	4.0	1.0	-	-	-	2.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.8	
T5.4	0.5	2.0	0.8	-	-	0.5	-	2.0	-	8.0	-	3.0	-	-	-	-	0.5	-	-	33.5	-	-	50.8	
T5.5	-	-	-	-	-	16.0	-	-	-	-	-	6.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	22.0	
WP6	4.0	39.0	2.3	3.0	1.5	0.5	-	30.0	-	1.0	1.0	2.0	15.0	-	-	2.3	1.5	-	-	6.0	-	-	109.0	
T6.1	2.0	6.0	1.0	0.5	1.5	-	-	-	-	-	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.0	
T6.2	2.0	10.0	1.3	-	-	0.5	-	-	-	1.0	-	2.0	-	-	-	2.3	1.5	-	-	-	-	-	20.5	
T6.3	-	23.0	-	2.5	-	-	-	30.0	-	-	-	-	15.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.0	-	-	76.5	

WP7	8.5	35.0	6.5	5.0	6.5	5.5	2.0	9.0	-	5.0	2.0	1.0	22.0	-	-	1.5	0.5	-	1.0	-	23.5	-	134.5	
T7.1	8.5	4.0	3.3	-	6.5	-	2.0	-	-	2.5	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.4	-	-	-	28.2	
T7.2	-	9.0	3.3	5.0	-	-	-	-	-	2.5	1.0	1.0	4.0	-	-	1.5	0.5	-	0.4	-	-	-	28.2	
T7.3	-	20.0	-	-	-	-	-	9.0	-	-	-	-	14.0	-	-	-	-	-	0.2	-	-	-	43.2	
T7.4	-	2.0	-	-	-	1.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.5	
T7.5	-	-	-	-	-	4.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	23.5	-	31.5
WP8	40.0	22.0	4.5	-	-	-	25.0	-	9.4	2.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	102.9	
T8.1	4.0	-	1.3	-	-	-	6.0	-	-	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11.8	
T8.2	3.0	-	-	-	-	-	13.0	-	-	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16.5	
T8.3	-	13.0	1.3	-	-	-	-	-	9.4	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	24.2	
T8.4	17.0	5.0	1.5	-	-	-	6.0	-	-	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	30.0	
T8.5	16.0	4.0	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.5	
WP9	6.0	34.5	6.5	-	-	-	24.0	-	27.0	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.0	-	101.0	
T9.1	-	4.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	27.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	31.0	
T9.2	-	10.5	2.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	13.3	
T9.3	-	20.0	2.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	22.8	
T9.4	-	-	2.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.0	-	4.0	
T9.5	6.0	-	-	-	-	-	24.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	30.0	
WP10	3.5	30.0	1.5	1.0	0.9	-	3.5	1.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.5	4.0	-	0.8	1.5	2.0	18.5	2.0	4.0	1.0	14.0	94.7	
T10.1	0.5	2.0	0.3	0.3	0.2	-	-	1.0	0.2	0.5	-	0.5	1.0	-	-	0.5	-	5.0	0.6	3.0	-	4.0	19.5	
T10.2	0.5	2.0	0.3	0.3	0.2	-	1.3	-	1.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	-	0.8	0.5	1.0	7.0	0.8	1.0	1.0	3.0	23.8	
T10.3	1.3	1.0	0.3	-	-	-	1.3	-	-	-	-	-	1.0	-	-	-	-	3.5	-	-	-	1.0	9.3	
T10.4	-	23.0	0.5	-	-	-	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.5	-	-	-	1.0	27.0	
T10.5	1.3	2.0	0.3	0.5	0.5	-	-	-	0.1	-	0.5	0.5	1.0	-	-	0.5	1.0	1.5	0.6	-	-	5.0	15.2	
WP11	1.0	3.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	-	1.0	0.5	18.0	1.0	1.0	1.5	9.0	9.0	0.5	0.8	0.5	1.0	1.0	-	-	11.0	61.8	
T11.1	0.5	-	0.3	-	-	-	-	0.2	-	0.5	0.5	0.3	3.0	-	-	-	0.2	0.3	0.3	-	-	6.0	11.9	
T11.2	-	-	0.3	-	-	-	1.0	0.1	-	-	0.5	0.3	4.0	-	-	-	0.2	0.3	0.3	-	-	4.0	10.8	
T11.3	-	2.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	-	-	0.1	18.0	-	-	-	1.0	-	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	-	0.5	23.7	
T11.4	0.5	1.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	-	-	0.1	-	0.5	-	1.0	1.0	9.0	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	-	0.5	15.4	
WP12	4.0	30.0	6.3	-	-	-	-	1.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.5	2.0	-	-	-	53.1	
T12.1	2.0	6.0	1.0	-	-	-	-	1.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11.4	
T12.2	2.0	18.0	3.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.0	-	-	-	-	24.3	
T12.3	-	6.0	2.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.5	-	-	-	-	17.5	
TOTAL	110.5	227.5	53.5	18.0	13.0	44.0	66.5	107.0	58.7	66.0	39.0	65.5	104.0	9.0	10.8	29.5	24.5	30.0	15.0	44.5	25.5	44.0	###	

The estimated lump sum shares indicated in Annex 2 can be adjusted by transfers of amounts between beneficiaries and/or work packages, via an amendment (see Article 55, DoA).

V. QUALITY ASSURANCE AND CONTROL TOOLS

The following tools and techniques have been and will continue to be used for project planning, management, and control, including the quality criteria to be collected and reported during the project:

Table 3: Quality tools for project management.

Tools Name	Frequency	Tolerance
WP Status reports distributed	Bi-Monthly	One month (i.e. every two months).
WP Progress Reports distributed	Bi-annually	One month
WP Project Review (following completion of WP Progress Report)	Bi-annually	One month
Deliverables reviews	Per Deliverable	No tolerance.
Milestone reviews executed	Per milestone	No tolerance.
Reporting period reviews executed	Per reporting period	No tolerance.
Stakeholders' satisfaction questionnaires sent, received and analysed	Once during the project	No tolerance.

Table 4: Project meetings.

Meeting Name	Frequency	Tolerance
Project Management (Coordinator and Project Management team) Meetings	Weekly	One week. Holiday period, each three weeks.
Project Technical Innovation Board (TIB) meetings performed	Quarterly	One month (i.e. every three months).
WPL meetings	Once every 6 months	One month (i.e. every three months).
Project Review Meetings	Once every 18 months	No tolerance.

The past 2 years made the PM team decide that it is better to gather the WP status reports once every 2 months instead of once a month, so that the information collected is more concise, more accurate and finally this has allowed better planning for reports collection for the PM team and better reporting of the achievements and issues by the WPLs.

As per the needs of the project and its careful and on time monitoring new series of virtual meetings, called Work Package Leaders (WPLs) have been scheduled. They are carried out once every 6 months (every second one is the CM) in addition to the tools above. These regular meetings are organised among the WP Leaders, co-leaders and task leaders. WP decisions need verbal consensus between the PC, WPL and TL. WPLs report to the PC, while the TL (task leaders) will report to the WPL, the STL to the TL. All consortium members carry collective responsibility for project implementation and execution.

1. PROJECT DELIVERABLES

There has been no change in the section reflecting the Deliverables Review and Approval process – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p. 15).

As a summary – a total of 98 deliverables are to be submitted to the European Commission over the project implementation, 71 of which will be available to the public and will thus be accessible long after the project’s completion. Therefore, a review process is a key step in the preparation of the deliverable to guarantee that the result is up to the appropriate standard and to the quality expectations.

2. DELIVERABLE REQUIREMENTS

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p. 15).

3. REVIEWING PROCEDURE

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p. 16).

4. DELIVERABLES REVIEWING CHECKLIST

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p. 19) - Figure 2. Deliverables Reviewing Checklist.

The deliverables reviews are performed in three stages based on the *Deliverables Reviewing Checklist*, available at ownCloud shared space.

VI. PROJECT PROGRESS MEASUREMENT

1. WORK PACKAGE STATUS REPORTS

The project quality has been monitored and managed also through periodic reporting on the work package status, use of resources, risk and issues encountered and activities planning.

Every 2 months each Work Package leader fill in a 1-page Work Package Status Report. The Project Manager sends reminders each Work Package Leaders to do so 10 days before the end of the month. The template for the report is available on ownCloud.

2. WORK PACKAGE PROGRESS REPORTS

Additionally, all Work Package Leaders have been asked to report **every 6 months** all activities they have performed, risks or issues encountered within the respective work package (including technical activities, communication and dissemination activities etc.), using the Work Package Progress Report template. A reminder has been sent to each work package leader by the Project Manager 15 days before the deadline. WPLs are responsible to gather all the information on the technical progress in their WP from the task leaders (sub-task leaders) in their respective work package and compile a WP report before sending it to the coordinator and Project Manager. The template is available on ownCloud.

All work package Progress Reports are integrated as part of the Project Quality Reviews.

3. PROJECT QUALITY REVIEWS

All work performance quality reviews will be analysed and recommendation and remediation/improvement actions will be defined in the Quality Review Report.

Project quality reviews will be performed every six months to verify that all project plans and processes are executed as planned and at the expected quality. The objective of the internal report is to monitor the project's technical progress. It will be a summary of the technical work completed, progress on the work which is ongoing as well as an explanation for any deviations from Annex 1.

4. QUALITY CONTROL RECORDS

The quality records (evidence that quality management activities have been performed) are archived in the project repository (ownCloud), under the "Monitor & Control" folder. The different versions of the project artefacts (created at each artefact update) will provide evidence of the performance of these activities.

VII. RISK MANAGEMENT

In the preparation phase, the Consortium has created an initial risk list, which can be updated whenever new risks have been identified. The preliminary list of potential project risks and mitigating actions is included in the Grant Agreement, Section 1.3.5. WT5 Critical Implementation risks and mitigation actions.

1. RISK IDENTIFICATION AND DESCRIPTION

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p34).

2. RISK ASSESSMENT AND RESPONSE

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p34).

3. RISK RESPONSE

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p35).

4. RISK CONTROL – RISK REGISTER

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p35).

VIII. ISSUE MANAGEMENT

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p37).

Issue management aims to ensure that issues that have a potential impact on project scope, time, cost, quality, risk, or stakeholder satisfaction are assessed and acted upon. Relevant issues will be logged and followed-up and key decisions will be documented to bring visibility and accountability as to how and by whom they are taken, and to whom they should be communicated.

The issue management process for this project is a four-step process and falls under the responsibilities of the Project Manager (PM) who should execute the process when required throughout the project lifecycle:

1. ISSUE IDENTIFICATION

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p37).

2. ISSUE ASSESSMENT AND ACTION RECOMMENDATION

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p37).

3. ACTIONS IMPLEMENTATION

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p37).

4. ISSUE CONTROL – ISSUE LOG

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p37).

IX. CONFIGURATION MANAGEMENT

The purpose of the project configuration management process is to help project stakeholders to manage project artefacts effectively and to provide a single reliable reference to them, ensuring that the correct versions are available to the relevant parties. Additionally, it helps the Project Manager (PM) to identify the latest state of project artefacts and be able to gather all sources, documents, and other information for the project, prevent unauthorised changes, guarantee artefacts traceability, and return to previous versions (fall-back procedure).

There has been no change in this section – for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p. 40).

X. QUALITY OF PROJECT COMMUNICATION

Controlling project communications ensures optimal information flow so that stakeholders receive the necessary information at the right time. Communications must be controlled throughout the project life cycle. Some information will require more frequent communication and will be driven by stakeholder needs.

The NAUTILOS project has determined a set of guidelines with regards to the quantity and quality of the project communication, both internal and external as there has been no major change in the organization of the communication (for reference – D1.4 Quality plan (p42).

- Weekly between the Project Coordinator (CNR) and the Project Manager (EP);
- Bi-monthly (depending on the intensity of the work) WP/set of WPs meetings in ongoing work packages
- Every three months between TIB members:
- WPL meetings every 6 months

- Management meetings (every 6 months)
- External Advisory Board Meetings
- General Assembly meetings (during MMs, every 6 months)
- Other, ad-hoc meetings

XI. CONCLUSION

The Final Quality Plan is a non-separable part of the first Quality Plan drafted as D1.4 which has proven to be effectively guiding the project coordination and management on the pathway towards successful implementation of the activities described in the Grant Agreement.

It represents a useful tool to monitor activities, identify and mitigate potential risks, and ensure the successful execution of the project. It is shared with the consortium for a guide to efficient and transparent implementation of the common project.

XII. APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

NAUTILOS Final Quality Plan has been developed in accordance with the provision outlined within the following related documents:

- NAUTILOS Grant Agreement Nr. 101000825,
- NAUTILOS Consortium Agreement.

Alongside to these key documents, this plan has been developed on the basis of various project deliverables such as D1.1 Report on Management procedures (M2), D10.1 Outreach, Communication & Dissemination Strategy (M2), D1.3 Data Management Plan (M6), D1.4. Quality Plan (M3) and D11.1 NAUTILOS Exploitation Strategy (M3), D10.8 Outreach, Communication & Dissemination strategy 2 (M18).

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	NAUTILOS Grant Agreement Nr. 101000825	NAUTILOS ownCloud
2	NAUTILOS Consortium Agreement	NAUTILOS ownCloud
3	D1.1. Report on Management Procedures	NAUTILOS ownCloud
4	D10.1 Outreach, Communication and Dissemination Strategy	NAUTILOS ownCloud
5	D1.4 Quality Plan	NAUTILOS ownCloud
6	D10.8 Outreach, Communication & Dissemination strategy 2 (M18)	NAUTILOS ownCloud